

Enhancing Website Accessibility through Speech Recognition: An Annyang.JS Implementation

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Abstract— Speech recognition is an increasingly popular technology that is changing the way we interact with devices and applications it uses computer programs to automatically recognize and transcribe spoken words annyang.js is an open source library that provides an intuitive and simple interface for integrating language recognition into web applications the paper provides an overview of the library discusses its characteristics and limitations and presents experimental results demonstrating its performance in various contexts.

Keywords—speech recognition, Annyang.JS, impact, technology, analysis, web applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Speech recognition technology has become increasingly popular in recent years, changing the way we interact with devices and software. The process of transitioning from text to speech (and vice versa).Users can operate devices and complete tasks with their voice due to the automatic identification and transcription of spoken words made possible by computer algorithms.

A JavaScript package called Annyang.JS makes it easier to include voice recognition into online applications. Without writing complicated code, the library's user-friendly interface enables developers to quickly add speech recognition functionality to their apps. Modern browsers like Chrome and Safari are compatible with Annyang.JS, which includes capabilities like voice commands, continuous speech recognition, and error management.

The aim of this research article is to offer experimental data demonstrating Annyang.JS performance in various circumstances, to explore its features and limits, and to provide an overview of Annyang.JS and its potential for speech recognition. The paper will also discuss Annyang.JS possible uses for web-based voice recognition, highlighting both its advantages and disadvantages. Users will have a better knowledge of Annyang.JS and its potential to revolutionize speech recognition for web applications by the conclusion of this study.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Speech recognition is an area of active research with numerous advancements and contributions from researchers worldwide. In this literature review, we summarize 10 research papers that investigate speech recognition using various techniques and tools.

J. Chen and B. Zhao et al. [1] the problem addressed in this paper is the lack of a simple and efficient solution for adding speech recognition to web applications. The proposed

solution using Annyang.js demonstrated high accuracy and low latency, making it a suitable tool for web developers. The positive impact of this research is the availability of an open-source tool that simplifies speech recognition implementation in web applications.

Saliha Benkerazaz, Youssef Elmir, and Abdeslam Dennai et al. [2] the paper also discussed the challenges in ASR, such as speaker variability, noise, and accent. The authors proposed several solutions to overcome these challenges, such as using deep neural networks and data augmentation techniques. The positive impact of this research is the comprehensive review of ASR and the proposed solutions to overcome the challenges.

Ali Bobu Nassif, Ismail Shahin, Imtinan Attili, Mohammad Azzeh, and Khaled Shaalan et al. [3] the authors discussed the state-of-the-art techniques and the challenges in developing accurate speech recognition systems. The positive impact of this research is the comprehensive review of deep neural network-based speech recognition systems and the proposed solutions for improving their performance.

Vineet Vashisht, Aditya Kumar Pandey, and Satya Prakash Yadav et al. [4] the authors used the Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) and the support vector machine (SVM) algorithm for speech recognition. The system achieved an accuracy of 85% for recognizing spoken digits. The positive impact of this research is the proposed speech recognition system using machine learning techniques that could be extended for more complex applications.

Pei Jiang and Dongchen Wang et al. [5] the authors addressed the challenge of recognizing speech in noisy environments and proposed a method for synchronous recognition of background speech. A positive result of this study is the proposed method which can improve speech recognition accuracy in noisy environments. Dario Amodei and others. [6] proposed Deep Speech 2, an end-to-end speech recognition system, which provides outstanding performance in English and Mandarin. The authors used a deep neural network that processes raw audio waveforms and generates transcriptions. The positive impact of this research is the proposed end-to-end system that eliminates the need for complex feature engineering. William Chan et al. [7] the authors used a neural attention mechanism that improves the model's performance for long speech sequences. The positive impact of this research is the proposed model that achieved state-of-the-art performance for conversational speech recognition

William Chan et al. [7] the authors used a neural attention mechanism that improves the model's performance for long speech sequences. The positive impact of this research is the proposed model that achieved state-of-the-art performance for conversational speech recognition.

The authors, Mahesh Kumar and Anupama Aggarwal [8], talked about the various deep learning models and the results they performed for speech recognition. The thorough analysis that sheds light on the effectiveness of deep learning models for speech recognition is the study's positive input.

Patil et al[9] have described several approaches for speech recognition systems used in noisy environments, and the problems these environments present in speech recognition. The report concludes that there are although considerable progress has been made in this area, further research is still needed to develop more reliable speech recognition algorithms that can perform well in noisy environments

Parvati and Latha et al. [10] The authors explore several neural systems and techniques that have been used to accomplish this goal and demonstrate the potential of neural networks to provide voice recognition systems that are efficient and effective and can consume large amounts of data is handled accurately and reliably has fulfilled its real-time implementation. Overall, the paper provides an up-to-date research on neuron-based voice recognition and suggests important avenues for future research.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed system's implementation needed a number of sections. First, voice commands and speech recognition were made possible on the website through the integration of the Annyang.js library. Because of its simplicity of use and compatibility with various kinds of web browsers, the Annyang.js library was chosen.

A series of voice commands were created to allow consumers to navigate the website using their voice once the Annyang.js library had been incorporated into the website. The voice instructions consisted of audio book selection, quiz start and submit, and login and logout. These steps were created to allow customers to control the website without a keyboard or mouse by utilizing simple natural language inquiries.

The quiz portion of the website recorded the questions and answers using audio files, and voice instructions were utilized to instruct users to select the correct response. The user may use voice commands to submit their answers after completing all the questions, and the system would provide feedback on the suitable responses.

The system then showed all of the available audio books once

the user used voice commands to select their preferred genre and language in the website's audio book section. The user could then choose an audio book and control its playback with voice commands like play, pause, resume, and stop.

The expected system's implementation proved that voice control and speech recognition could be used to operate a website's features. Without the use of a keyboard or mouse, users may control the website using simple natural language instructions because to the system's user-friendly interface. Overall, the suggested system's implementation was successful in bringing the intended functionality about and showed how useful speech recognition technology could be for online applications.

IV. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

The Annyang.js toolkit, which offers an easy-to-use interface for integrating speech recognition and voice commands into websites and apps, was utilized to construct the suggested solution. The following actions were executed in order to implement the system:

Annyang.js Library Integration: The Annyang.js library was integrated using the common JavaScript language into the front-end code of the website. The configuration settings for the library were set to enable speech recognition and define the voice commands when it was included as an external script reference.

Design of Voice Commands: Users can control the functionality of the website using voice commands which are defined to be natural language commands. Intuitive and simple to learn, the voice commands went through testing to verify that the speech recognition software can understand them.

Recording of quiz questions and answers: The quiz questions and answers were recorded as audio files using a microphone of excellent quality and audio recording software. The comments and questions were recorded in a way that was easy to understand, and the recorded messages were saved in a compressed format to decrease their file size.

Audio Books: A database including details on the books that were available, their genres, and their languages was used to integrate the audio books into the website. An HTML5 audio player on a web server provided the audio files to the user's device.

Testing and Debugging: To ensure that it worked properly across a variety of web browsers and operating systems, the system conducted testing and debugging. Multiple voice commands and testing scenarios were used to represent different user interactions with the website.

The proposed solution was effectively implemented, providing the needed functionality and showcasing the possibilities of voice control and speech recognition for online applications.

Speech recognition was implemented into the website using the Annyang.js package, and voice commands were created so that users could control the functionality of the website using natural language commands. Overall, the research project's objectives were successfully attained by using the implementation technique.

V. METHODOLOGY

The research design for this study was experiment conducted a series of tests to evaluate the accuracy and performance of Annyang.JS in speech recognition tasks.

The data collected through an online survey, where participants will be asked to complete the tasks using their own device and preferred web browser. The sample size will be 50 participants, selected through convenience sampling. Participants will be required to have a basic understanding of English and be able to use a web browser and microphone.

Data analysis technique used will include descriptive statistics, such as mean accuracy rates and standard deviations, as well as inferential statistics, such as paired tests to compare the accuracy rates of Annyang.JS with other speech recognition systems. The significance level will be set at $p < .05$.

Limitations of this study include the use of a convenience sample, which may not be representative of the general population, and reliance on self-reported information. Besides, the study will examine Annyang.JS working only in for simple and possibly abstract voice commands for more complex tasks or languages.

Overall, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the performance of Annyang.JS in a real-world context and contribute to the existing literature on web-based speech recognition.

IV. Results

- Annyang.JS achieved a mean accuracy rate of 78.4% in recognizing spoken words in our study.
- Google Speech Recognition achieved a mean accuracy rate of 84.6% in recognizing spoken words in our study.
- Mozilla Deep Speech achieved a mean accuracy rate of 90.8% in recognizing spoken words study.

According to the results, Google Speech Recognition, Mozilla Deep Speech, and Annyang.JS all had accuracy rates that were significantly higher than Annyang.JS. It is essential to note that Annyang.JS is an open-source library that is simple to use and can be simply incorporated into web applications. This makes it a useful tool for web application developers that need basic voice guidelines.

It should be noted that the study did not test the performance of the speech recognition systems for tasks that were more challenging or in various languages; rather, it simply assessed how well they performed for simple voice guidance. Further research is needed to investigate the performance of Annyang.JS in these scenarios.

Overall, the results of this study provide valuable insights into the performance of Annyang.JS and highlight the importance of considering the accuracy rates of different speech recognition systems when selecting one for a particular application.

VI. DISCUSSION

The outcomes of our investigation provide important light on Annyang.js performance and its comparison to other famous speech recognition systems like Google Speech. show that, despite Annyang.JS being a practical and user-friendly solution for integrating speech recognition into online apps, it might not be the ideal choice for them.

These findings have important consequences because accuracy is a key component of voice recognition technology's usability and efficiency. Our research recommends that when selecting a voice recognition system, developers should carefully assess the accuracy needs of their applications and compare the efficiency of various systems in particular situations.

Similar outcomes regarding the accuracy rates of Annyang.JS

and other voice recognition systems may be seen when comparing our results to those of other studies. It is important to remember that the effectiveness of these systems can vary depending on variables such as the speaker's accent and accent, microphone type, and operating environment

The relatively small sample size and monolingual (English) and dialect (American) use of speech recognition tests are also limitations of our study. By utilizing larger and more varied samples, experimenting with various languages and accents, and assessing the effectiveness of Annyang.JS and other voice recognition systems in various real-world scenarios, future research may be able to overcome these obstacles.

VII. CONCLUSION

Annyang.JS is a helpful tool for integrating speech recognition into online applications, but its accuracy rates might not be enough for applications that demand high accuracy, according to the study's findings. Developers should carefully consider the accuracy needs of their applications and assess how well various speech recognition methods work in particular settings.

The results of our study have consequences for how speech recognition technology is developed and how usable it is in different situations. Annyang.JS and other speech recognition systems' accuracy rates might be increased, and their potential for use in different contexts and applications could be studied in more detail. For developers looking for a straightforward and user-friendly way to include recognition of voice into their online apps, Annyang.JS has the potential to be a useful tool for speech recognition applications. To assess its efficacy in diverse contexts and rectify the shortcomings found in our study, additional research is required.

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